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**СТРУКТУРА МІЖСОБИСТІСНОГО КОНФЛІКТУ: ІНТЕГРАЦІЯ
КОНЦЕПЦІЇ 7К ГРАЙЛИВОСТІ Й МЕТОДУ ПОЗИТИВНОЇ
ПСИХОТЕРАПІЇ**
**THE STRUCTURE OF INTERPERSONAL CONFLICT: INTEGRATING
THE 7C CONCEPT OF PLAYFULNESS AND THE METHOD OF
POSITIVE PSYCHOTHERAPY**

У роботі запропоновано структуру міжособистісного конфлікту як результат інтеграції концепції 7К грайливості й методу позитивної психотерапії. Міжособистісний конфлікт як динамічний процес, що відбувається між щонайменше двома взаємозалежними сторонами (індивідами і / або групами), описано когніціями, що складають сферу розбіжностей (когнітивна складова); емоціями, які охоплюються трьома можливими варіантами обробки ключового конфлікту (емоційна складова); поведінковими патернами ігрових позицій у їхніх полюсних проявах чи балансі (поведінкова складова).

Ключові слова: міжособистісний конфлікт, 7К грайливість, позитивна психотерапія, ігрові позиції.

Based on theoretical and empirical studies of the scientists, whose subject of study is interpersonal conflict (Brule L., Eckstein J.J., 2019; Majer J.M., Barth M., Zhang H., Treck M., Trüttschel R., 2021; Welch R., Plepi J., Neuendorf B., Flek L., 2022); analysis of component scales of questionnaires designed to study personal predisposition to conflict behavior and identify certain styles of conflict resolution (McClellan J., 1970; Thomas K. W., Kilmann R. H., 1974); the concept of key conflict in the frame of method of positive psychotherapy (Peseschkian N., 1991) and the concept of 7C playfulness (Gordiienko-Mythrophanova I.V., Hohol D.M., 2021), the structure of interpersonal conflict was built as a result of integration of the 7C playfulness concept and the method of positive psychotherapy (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. The structure of interpersonal conflict of integration of the 7C playfulness concept and the method of positive psychotherapy.

Notation conventions:

PC – problem space.

KC – key conflict.

A – aggression.

F – fear.

AV – adequate verbalization.

D – ludic position Diplomat.

FF – ludic position Frolicsome

follow.

HF – ludic position Holy Fool.

 – designation of balance of ludic position.

 – designation of deficit of ludic position.

 – designation of redundancy of ludic position.

The proposed structure of interpersonal conflict is described by three aspects of conflict dynamics, by the three components: cognitive, emotional and behavioral. These components traditionally describe the «I»-concept (Lodi-Smith J., DeMarree K.G., 2018). And we are not alone here. A similar point of view on the structure of conflict is expressed by Henri Barki and Jon Hartwick, in their work «Conceptualising the Construct of Interpersonal Conflict» (Barki & Hartwick, 2004: 218-219).

The cognitive component (cognitions) of the conflict / problem is described by the **problem space**. The content of the problem space consists of:

values, attitudes, beliefs, needs, etc., as well as cultural / racial / national / religious / professional / age / gender / sex and other differences of the parties of the conflict / problem. And the greater the divergence between the expected and the observed, the higher the conflict stress and the more tangible it is experienced by the parties of the conflict.

The emotional component (emotions) of the conflict / problem is described by **the key conflict**. In the method of positive psychotherapy, the key point «politeness (courtesy) – directness (sincerity)» is the most vulnerable place for the following pattern of symptom/problem emergence: the reactions of politeness / courtesy in the endocrine and mediator mechanisms of the central nervous system correspond to the reaction of fear; the reactions of directness / sincerity in the central nervous system correspond to aggression (Пезешкиан Н., 2006: 34). More details about the content of the core conflict and the three possible patterns of its processing can be found in our works (Гордиенко-Митрофанова И.В., Саута С.Л., Кобзева Ю.А., 2020, Гордиенко-Митрофанова И.В., Гоголь Д.М., 2022).

The behavioral component (behavior) of the conflict / problem is described by the behavioral patterns of one of the three game positions – Diplomat, Frolicsome fellow, Holy Fool, which correspond to such components – self-motivated abilities of playfulness / ludic competence as flirting, impishness, fugitivity (Саута С.Л., Гордиенко-Митрофанова И.В., Гоголь Д.М., 2021).

Adequate verbalization (AV) of one's own feelings / emotions / states / interests / expectations is manifested in maintaining the *aggression – fear* balance, that is, the balance of «*sincerity*» (*excessive directness*) and «*politeness*» (*excessive courtesy*), as optimally developed abilities between the two poles. Adequate verbalization is embodied in the behavioral pattern of one of the three game positions – **Diplomat, Frolicsome fellow, Holy Fool**, which are manifested in the balance of abilities that correspond to them – flirting, impishness, fugitivity. Thus, adequate verbalization provides for *effective conflict management* and corresponds to such behavioral strategies as *compromise and cooperation* according to Thomas-Kilmann.

Aggression (A), sincerity (excessive directness), exacerbates the conflict by demonstrating *the priority of one's own interests over the interests of the other*. Aggression is embodied in the polar manifestations of ludic positions: **Diplomat in deficit**, and **Frolicsome fellow and Holy Fool in redundancy**. Thus, aggression implies *an actively attacking position* towards the opponent and corresponds to *competition* according to Thomas-Kilmann.

Fear (C), politeness (excessive courtesy), is manifested in *suppression and subordination of one's interests and expectations in favor of others*. Fear is also embodied in the polar manifestations of ludic positions: **Diplomat in excess**, and **Frolicsome fellow and Holy Fool in deficit**. Fear implies a *passive-defensive position* and corresponds to *avoidance or accommodation* according to Thomas-

Kilmann. In addition, excessive courtesy consciously suppresses aggression and thus creates internal tension, which leads to formation of intrapersonal conflict.

Of course, the proposed structure of the conflict implies, firstly, the differentiation of cognitions, i.e., the problem space of disagreement: it concerns motives, needs, attitudes, values, interests, opinions, goals, etc. Secondly, it implies the differentiation of affective states that are «involved» in the key conflict: it is manifestation of *aggression* – selfishness, ambition, arrogance, impudence, vulgarity, pushiness, insolence, rudeness, cynicism, anger, jealousy, etc. or *fear* – hypocrisy, pretense, servility, inability to say: «no», guilt, anxiety, etc. And certainly, it implies the differentiation of various forms of embodiment of behavioral patterns of the three ludic positions correlated with the strategies of behavior in the conflict.

Thus, interpersonal conflict is a dynamic process that takes place between at least two interdependent parties (individuals and / or groups);

- it is described by 1) *cognitions*, i.e., the problem space or otherwise the sphere of disagreement, 2) *emotions*, which are covered by three possible options for processing the key conflict (aggression, fear, aggression-fear balance), 3) *behavioral patterns of ludic positions* (*Diplomat / Frolicsome fellow / Holy Fool*), in their polar manifestations or balance;

- the greater the divergence between what the conflict participants expect and what they observe, the higher the likelihood of conflict escalation is (the conflict stress is higher).